

Conductometric Studies on the Complexes of Cu(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Mn(II) and Fe(III) with Pyrophosphoric Acid

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Manuscript received 24 June 1975; accepted 14 August 1975

This technique of conductometry gave qualitative measure of the nature of reaction products obtained through different reaction steps. The course of the reactions has been explained on these electrometric studies. Furthermore, the colloidal nature of the reaction products and the tendency to polymerise, may be foretold with the help of this technique.

INVESTIGATIONS on the composition of heavy metal pyrophosphates have been carried out by a number of workers.¹⁻¹⁴ Rogers and Reynolds carried out studies on the composition and stability of the complexes with the help of conductometric and potentiometric titration. Since, however, the sodium pyrophosphate used in these studies is quite unstable¹⁵⁻¹⁶ in aqueous solution, the resulting complexes may have dubious composition. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile to reinvestigate the metal pyrophosphate reaction by employing pyrophosphoric acid as the reacting species. In this paper we report the result of conductometric titrations between heavy metal salts and pyrophosphoric acid.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions: All the metal salts were of Analar Grade (B. D. H. products). Pyrophosphoric acid used were of E. MERCK products. The solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water.

Apparatus: The conductivity Bridge CLOI/OIA (INDIA) was used for conductance measurement. Dip type conductivity cell was kept immersed in a thermostatic waterbath maintained at a temperature of $25^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$.

Procedure: 10 ml (0.01M) of the metal salts solution was taken in the conductivity cell. 0.2 ml of the titrant from the micro-burette at a time was added to the solution cell. After each addition the solution was stirred and the conductivity recorded. Both direct (metal salt in the cell) and reverse (pyrophosphoric acid in the cell) titrations were performed.

Results and Discussion

Curve I and II in Fig. 1-5 show the direct and reverse conductometric titrations of metal salts and pyrophosphoric acid. Two stages of reactions are obtained in case of the nickel chloride while in case of rest of the metal salts, viz., cupric chloride, cobalt nitrate, manganese chloride, ferric and nitrate, the reaction gets completed in three stages. In the direct titration, the reaction may be represented according to

Fig. 1

Curve I: Conductometric titration of (0.01M) Cu^{2+} 10 ml vs 0.1M $\text{H}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$.

II: Conductometric titration of (0.01M) $\text{H}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ 10 ml vs 0.1M Cu^{2+} .

the following general equations

Fig. 2

Curve I: Conductometric titration of 10 ml (0.01M) Co^{2+} vs $0.1M \text{H}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$.

II: Conductometric titration of 10 ml (0.01M) $\text{H}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ vs $0.1M \text{Co}^{2+}$.

Fig. 3

Curve I: Conductometric titration of (0.01M) Ni^{2+} 10 ml vs $0.1M \text{H}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$.

II: Conductometric titration of (0.01M) $\text{H}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ 10 ml vs $0.1M \text{Ni}^{2+}$.

Fig. 4

Curve I: Conductometric titration of 10 ml (0.01M) Mn^{2+} vs $0.1M \text{H}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$

II: Conductometric titration of 10ml(0.01M) $\text{H}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ vs. $0.1M \text{Mn}^{2+}$.

Fig. 5

Curve I: Conductometric titration of (0.01M) Fe^{3+} 10 ml vs $0.1M \text{H}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$.

II: Conductometric titration of (0.01M) $\text{H}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ 10 ml vs $0.1M \text{Fe}^{3+}$.

In the case of reverse titrations, the following reaction scheme is proposed :

For example, the first break at 2 : 1 (metal : pyrophosphate) in the direct titration of copper with pyrophosphoric acid may be represented in accordance with the following equation

The second break at 2 : 3 may be expressed as,

The third break at 2 : 4 may be defined according to the following equations

The relevant information thus obtained regarding the stoichiometry of the chemical species formed at different steps is given in Table 1. With regard to assessing the role of hydrogen ions in these reactions, pH metric studies were found adequate for this purpose (unpublished work).

Another interesting aspect of the studies on these metal pyrophosphates is that some of the ionic species form negatively charged colloidal solutions of varying stability (Table 2). This behaviour definitely points to the formation of bigger aggregates through polymerisation of the ionic species.

Evidence of the existence of polymeric species :

The composition of the various complexes as determined by conductometry reveal that, in most cases polymeric anions are formed. This behaviour is justifiable on the basis of the following facts :

(i) Like other metal phosphates, the heavy metal pyrophosphates under discussion give colloidal solution of high stability. Concentrated solutions give gels by the method of double decomposition (details to be published elsewhere).

(ii) The mode of coordination of the pyrophosphate ion with the metal can facilitate polymerisation either through direct addition or by the hydrolysis of the reaction product.

TABLE 1

Metal salt	Stoichiometric ratios		Products formed direct titration	Products formed reverse titration
	direct titration metal : pyrophosphate	Reverse titration metal : pyrophosphate		
CuCl ₂	2 : 1	1 : 2	[Cu ₂ H ₂ P ₂ O ₇] ²⁺	[Cu(H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₂] ²⁻
	2 : 3	3 : 2	[Cu ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₃] ²⁻	[Cu ₃ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₂] ²⁺
	2 : 4	4 : 2	[Cu ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₄] ⁴⁻	[Cu ₄ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₂] ⁴⁺
Co(NO ₃) ₂	2 : 1	1 : 2	[Co ₂ (OH) ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇)]	[Co(OH)(H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₂] ³⁻
	2 : 2	2 : 2	[Co ₂ (OH) ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₂] ²⁻	[Co ₂ (OH) ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₂] ²⁻
	2 : 3	3 : 2	[Co ₂ (OH) ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₃] ⁴⁻	[Co ₃ (OH) ₃ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₂] ⁻
NiCl ₂	1 : 1	1 : 2	[NiH ₂ P ₂ O ₇]	[Ni(H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₂] ²⁻
	1 : 2	2 : 2	[Ni(H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₂] ²⁻	[Ni ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₄]
MnCl ₂	2 : 2	2 : 4	[Mn ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₂]	[Mn ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₄] ⁴⁻
	2 : 3	3 : 4	[Mn ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₃] ²⁻	[Mn ₃ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₄] ²⁻
	2 : 4	4 : 4	[Mn ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₄] ⁴⁻	[Mn ₄ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₄]
Fe(NO ₃) ₃	2 : 2	2 : 4	[Fe ₂ (OH) ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₂]	[Fe ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₄] ²⁻
	2 : 3	3 : 4	[Fe ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₃]	[Fe ₃ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₄] ⁺
	2 : 4	4 : 4	[Fe ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₄] ²⁻	[Fe ₄ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₄] ⁴⁺

TABLE 2

Reactants	Reaction products	Metal to pyrophosphate ratio
Cu ²⁺ and H ₂ P ₂ O ₇ ²⁻	[Cu ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₂] ²⁻	2 : 3
	[Cu ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₄] ⁴⁻	2 : 4
Co(OH) ⁺ and H ₂ P ₂ O ₇ ²⁻	[Co ₂ (OH) ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₂] ²⁻	2 : 2
	[Co ₂ (OH) ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₃] ⁴⁻	2 : 3
Ni ²⁺ and H ₂ P ₂ O ₇ ²⁻	[Ni(H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₂] ²⁻	1 : 2
VO ²⁺ and H ₂ P ₂ O ₇	[VO ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₂] ²⁺	2 : 1
	[VO ₂ (H ₂ P ₂ O ₇) ₄] ⁴⁺	2 : 4

References

1. PERSOZ, *Ann. Chem. Phys.*, 1847, 20, 315.
2. SCHWARZENBERG, *Ann.*, 1848, 65, 133.
3. BAER, *Pogg. Ann.*, 1949, 75, 152.
4. FLEITMANN and HENNEBERG, *Ann.*, 1848, 65, 387.
5. PAHL, OBVERS, K. VANT., *Akad. Farh.*, 1973, 30, 29.
6. ROSENHUM and TRIATAPHYLLIDES, *Ber.*, 1915, 48, 582.
7. ROSENHEIM, FROMMER, GLASSER and HANDLER, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, 153, 126.
8. H. BASSETT, W. L. BEDWELL and J. B. HUTCHINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1412.
9. STARECK, *United States Patent* 2, 1941, 256, 556.
10. KOLIHOF and WATTERS, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1943, 15, 8.
11. PAKAL, *Compt. Rend.*, 1908, 146, 231.
12. B. H. GILMORE, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1937, 29, 584.
13. DWARZAK and REICH-ROHRWIG, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1929, 77, 14.
14. L. B. ROGERS and C. A. REYNOLDS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 2081.
15. J. P. GROWTHER, A. E. R. WESTMAN, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1954, 32, 42.
16. J. R. VANWAZER, E. J. GRIFFITH and J. F. McCULLOUGH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 287.